

NEOSUCCESS

Upscaling and Market Introduction of
Simultaneous Biogas Upgrading and Bio-
Succinic Acid Production

D6.4

FINAL REPORT ON D&C ACTIVITIES

NEOSUCCESS Project
Grant Agreement No. 950921

DOCUMENT TYPE (R/DEM/DEC/OTHER)

R_REPORT

DISSEMINATION LEVEL (PU/CO/CI)

PU-PUBLIC

Document information

Document history			
Issue	Date	Comment	Author
V1	05.10.2023	First version of the Deliverable	Sofía Veiga (NORVENTO)

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Document distribution		
Issue	Date	Distributed to
V1	05.10.2023	Consortium Partners

Verification and approval		
	Date	Name
Verification final Draft by WP leader	22.11.2023	Iago Jove (NORVENTO)
Approval Final Deliverable by coordinator	22.11.2023	Francisco Heredia (IVEM)

Disclaimer and acknowledgements

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 950921”

Horizon 2020
European Union Funding
for Research & Innovation

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
1. INTRODUCTION	5
2. OBJECTIVES.....	6
2.1. CONSORTIUM	6
2.2. WP6 TASKS.....	6
2.3. SCOPE OF THE DOCUMENT	7
3. INTERNAL COMMUNICATION	8
3.1. CONSORTIUM FACE-TO-FACE COMMUNICATIONS	8
3.2. CONSORTIUM ONLINE COMMUNICATION	10
3.3. EXTERNAL COMMUNICATION.....	10
4. D&C ACTIONS	11
4.1. ONLINE CHANNELS	11
4.2. OFFLINE CHANNELS.....	16
5. SUMMARY	24
6. CONCLUSIONS	29
INDEX OF FIGURES AND TABLES	30
FIGURES	30
TABLES	30

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In this **Deliverable D6.4: "Final report on D&C activities"** all the activities that have been carried out by the NEOSUCCESS consortium for the dissemination and communication of the project are collected and detailed.

It includes an update of the information described in the previous deliverable D6.3: "First year of the D&C plan implementation" where the activities carried out up to month 12 of the project were indicated and the corrective actions to improve the communication procedures were highlighted.

This deliverable explains all the KPI targets that the project had to satisfy and indicates their achievement, with photographic evidence and web links.

As a summary, the website achieved more than 1.000 visits/year, 4 scientific papers were published, 2 main videos were uploaded on YouTube (exceeding 500 views), around 100 posts on online platforms, more than 200 followers and participation in 14 events.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Deliverable 6.4: Final report on D&C activities is the result of Task 6.1 – Dissemination & Communication (M1-42) that belongs to WP6 – Dissemination & Communication (M1-42). NORVENTO, as the WP6 leader, oversees the definition of this plan and the coordination of the different actions involved.

It is worth to note that the scope of the Dissemination and Communication (D&C) Plan includes the identification of potential target markets and stakeholders, thus NORVENTO takes an important role in the design and implementation of this plan, being the Consortium member that takes care of the commercial-focused tasks of the project.

The **Deliverable D6.4** is closely related to other WP6 deliverables already submitted:

- **D6.1: NEOSUCCESS website with information about the NEOSUCCESS project, outcomes, results, meetings, etc. (M3).** It is essential to convey the most important concepts and ideas in order to reach through this online tool the highest number of potential stakeholders. The message transmitted must be concise and clear.
- **D6.2: D&C Plan (M3).** Its main objective is to outline the path for the most optimal strategy for the dissemination and communication of the NEOSUCCESS Project, focusing on its results and its expected impact in the society and environment. The plan covers the actions to be carried out during the 42 months period of the Project duration and settles the basis for its future development and exploitation.
- **D6.3: First year of the D&C plan implementation (M12).** This report highlights the execution of all the milestones, activities and fundamental actions that have been designed during the first year of the NEOSUCCESS project. It acts as a first check point to evaluate D&C Plan and help adopting any corrective actions, if needed, to improve the dissemination and communication procedures (*The D6.3 is the first review of the D6.2*).

2. OBJECTIVES

The general objective of this deliverable is to give an update of the final status of the compliance with the D&C plan and the KPIs set for the D&C efforts.

2.1. CONSORTIUM

The NEOSUCCESS' Consortium is integrated by 4 members. Each of the involved parties has a key role during and after the project in relation to the Dissemination of results.

PARTNER	Role during the NEOSUCCESS' project	Role after NEOSUCCESS' project	WP6 effort (D&C)
	Coordination, construction and operation of the industrial unit in their premises (WWTP).	Design the electromechanical system (software control) and annual maintenance service.	16
	Downstream process upscaling and support on industrial validation. Communication activities, and commercial & scalability strategy.	Commercialisation, construction, installation, and start-up of the NEOSUCCESS technology.	6,5
	Patent owner (key know-how) R&D support on scaling up.	R&D support on scaling up. Patent licencing to industry partners.	3
	Downstream processing prototype + upscaling at industrial site.	R&D support on the downstream processing.	4

Figure 1. NEOSUCCESS Partners & WP6 (D&C) effort.

- **IVEM (Coordinator):** Spanish water and energy engineering firm
- **NORVENTO:** Spanish engineering firm, biogas plant construction
- **DTU:** Dep. of Environmental Engineering
- **AUTH:** Greek School of Agriculture

2.2. WP6 TASKS

The D&C Plan covers all the activities that have been performed along the implementation of the WP6. These works are summarized in 3 major tasks:

Task 6.1 - Dissemination and Communication (M1-M42)

The main objectives of Task 6.1 are:

1. To build a NEOSUCCESS-related community that includes all relevant stakeholders and encourage long-term relations with potential clients.
2. Establish an easily recognizable NEOSUCCESS identity.

3. Raise awareness of NEOSUCCESS at national and international level.
4. To inform about NEOSUCCESS results and main outcomes and to raise the interest of potential key stakeholders.

Dissemination & Communication activities include: the NEOSUCCESS website, promotional video(s), newsletters, press releases, publications, posters, roll ups, leaflets, etc. and any other printed or online promotion material that is deemed necessary.

This task also included all activities that are related to the participation at specialised events such as trade fairs, congresses, and summits related to main target sectors. Results of this task are collected in the present deliverable (D6.4).

Task 6.2 - Demonstration and Promotional Activities (M32-M42)

The industrial unit installed at IVEM's facilities have been used for the demonstration activities. Three demonstration sessions were organized (2 online, 1 on-site) to raise awareness among the specific target groups (potential clients) about the technology and its benefits, and to ensure a successful market penetration of NEOSUCCESS. Results of this task are collected in D6.5.

Task 6.3 - Training Activities (M32-M42)

A series of 3 training sessions focusing on the operational and wider socio-economic benefits of the developed technology have been prepared and delivered by AUTH and DTU to the technical and managerial staff from the industry and their members, end-users, and to relevant actors beyond the consortium. Results and materials of this task are collected in D6.6.

2.3. SCOPE OF THE DOCUMENT

This document contains the review carried out from the M13 to M42 on the D&C Plan implementation and also provides an update of all the activities that have been carried out up until this final deliverable.

The D&C Plan is the core document outlining the NEOSUCCESS' dissemination and communication activities. This plan has been essential for a good coordination of all initiatives, defining the correct content of the messages adapted to each of the targeted audiences, getting the required D&C impact and effectively communicating the NEOSUCCESS results. Effective communication encourages interested stakeholders to actively participate in the NEOSUCCESS and enhance the visibility of its results.

This Dissemination and Communication Plan aimed to:

- Outline the main objectives of the dissemination and communication actions to be implemented along the 42 months of the NEOSUCCESS.
- Identify and describe the different groups of target audiences.
- Define the tools and channels to be used, the message and the activities required to reach each targeted audience(s).
- Effectively achieving and communicating the NEOSUCCESS' expected impacts.

3. INTERNAL COMMUNICATION

The internal communication refers to the communication which takes place between partners and project collaborators. It is essential to set efficient internal communication channels and protocols for the project's proper outcome.

3.1. CONSORTIUM FACE-TO-FACE COMMUNICATIONS

- **DSP Start-up. (M24 - May 2022): NORVENTO & IVEM**

In May 2022, NORVENTO visited the Paterna WWTP where the NEOSUCCESS pilot plant is located. The objective of this visit was to carry out, together with IVEM, the start-up of the DSP sub-unit.

- **Second start-up. Maintenance and cleaning of the DSP unit (M30 - November 2022): NORVENTO & IVEM**

Several months after the start-up of the DSP, NORVENTO decides to return to Paterna for maintenance and cleaning. Taking advantage of this visit, NORVENTO and IVEM meet to discuss in person the DSP batches and organize the remaining deliverables of the project.

Figure 2. NORVENTO's visit to operate the DSP together with IVEM at the Paterna WWTP.

- **Recording of the 2nd video of NEOSUCCESS. USP batches (M35 - April 2023): AUTH, DTU & IVEM**

In April 2023, the second NEOSUCCESS video was shot. For this recording the AUTH and DTU universities traveled to the Paterna WWTP and together with IVEM, they recorded different scenes where they explained the project and the production process, there in the pilot plant. USP process and unit were checked, and DSP batches were carried out during their visit.

Figure 3. Both Universities visit the WWTP to record the second NEOSUCCESS video and run the USP.

- **Last meeting of the whole Consortium in Paterna. DSP Batches (M36 - May 2023): NORVENTO, AUTH, DTU & IVEM**

In May, a face-to-face meeting of the Consortium was held in Paterna, where all members were able to witness the operation of the pilot plant and run new batches in both the USP and DSP. At the same time, videos were recorded for training activities.

Figure 4. Consortium meeting at NEOSUCCESS pilot, Paterna's WWTP.

3.2. CONSORTIUM ONLINE COMMUNICATION

Regularly, video calls, phone calls and emails have been exchanged between the members of the consortium, to maintain continuous communication and follow the work program. From M13 to M42, more than 15 online meetings have been held between the consortium members.

Figure 5. Online consortium meeting.

Every communication was recorded, stored, and distributed among all the members of the Consortium.

Additionally, the online meetings were recorded by the Project Coordinator or the organiser when the Project Coordinator could not be in attendance. The recordings are uploaded and made available for all consortium members.

3.3. EXTERNAL COMMUNICATION

External communication covers communication actions with:

- Key stakeholders actively involved with NEOSUCCESS and potential clients.
- General public, scientific community, policymakers, and external business professionals.
- Specific communication activities towards the EU Commission Services, e.g., email and phone calls with NEOSUCCESS officer, regular reports, deliverables, etc.

External communication channels will be discussed in detail in section 4: *D&C ACTIONS*.

4. D&C ACTIONS

D&C actions have been carried out mainly through online communication channels. These channels provide data analysis tools that allow the collection of large amounts of information. Although most of the activities have been carried out online, this last year of the project has been carried out in a more face-to-face manner. The specific analysis of this data is essential to understand the impact of the dissemination actions.

This section gathers all the D&C activities that have been carried out for the promotion of the NEOSUCCESS project.

4.1. ONLINE CHANNELS

WEBSITE

The NEOSUCCESS Projects counts with an official [website](#) presented in both Spanish and English. It was officially launched in 01/08/2020 and has been active since then (almost 4 years). As better described in D6.1, the website includes the following sections:

- The Project: Including a general description of the NEOSUCCESS Project.
- Partners: Including information and links related to each Consortium Member.
- Documents: Compiling several documents, such as press releases.
- Links: Showing links to interesting related topics, such as portals.
- Agenda: Showing all publications posted in the website.
- Newsletter: Allowing to subscribe to the newsletter.
- Contact: Including information related to the Project Coordinator and how to contact him.

Figure 6. Headline of the website

On this website several posts have been uploaded monthly updating the progress of the project to the followers, summing up to 105 posts. Posts and other activities resulted in more than 5.300 visits (Table 1) from inside and outside of Europe (ESP, DNK, HEL, USA, NLD, FRA, DEU, UK, CHN, IND).

Table 1. NEOSUCCESS website visits per year.

M1-M12	1.719
M13-M24	1.461
M25-M36	1.222
M37-M42	913

Figure 7

Figure 8. Screenshot of the website section where new posts are uploaded.

KPI: 1.000 Visits/year – ACHIEVED

NEWSLETTERS

Along the Project’s duration, several newsletters have been launched to all mails subscribed in the mailing list. Previous to the newsletters, posts were published in the social media and website in order to ensure wider repercussion.

Figure 9. Example of cover of the NEOSUCCESS newsletter.

Table 2 compiles the NEOSUCCESS newsletters published:

Table 2. NEOSUCCESS published Newsletters.

1	13.10.2020	Link
2	13.10.2020	Link
3	23.10.2020	Link
4	29.06.2021	Link
5	27.05.2022	Link
6	26.05.2023	Link
7	21.11.2023	Link

TWITTER

The Twitter account was created on 09/07/2020 by the name [@NEOSUCCESSP](#). This platform is a social network with a very wide range of public and purposes, including professional and scientific content networks. Furthermore, the platform includes an analytical section, allowing to study the impacts of the profile.

The account has 216 followers to the date and includes around 85 tweets.

Figure 10. Screenshot of the Twitter's profile.

KPI: 200 Followers – ACHIEVED

LINKEDIN

The LinkedIn account was launched in 29/07/2020 by the name [NEOSUCCESS Consortium](#) and creating a “company” by the name [NeoSuccess Project](#). This platform is a business orientated social network where skilled audience (people and companies) attends to obtain more professional information and news. Furthermore, this platform also includes an analytical section, allowing to study the impacts of the profile.

The consortium has been very active on this social network, sharing information and posting regularly. The account has 229 followers to the date and includes approximately 90 posts.

Figure 11. Screenshots of the Project's LinkedIn.

KPI: 200 Followers – ACHIEVED

YOUTUBE

YouTube is a videographic content open platform, hence an account by the name [@neosuccessproject2647](https://www.youtube.com/@neosuccessproject2647) was created in 06/08/2020 to disseminate videos from the Project and the partners. Just as the other social network platforms, this one allows to revise the statistics of the videos.

Figure 12. Screenshot of the YouTube account

Previously, during 2022 (RP2), the first NEOSUCCESS video ([3' video](#)) was uploaded to raise awareness about the sustainable production of BioSuccinic Acid and BioMethane.

In this 2023, the second NEOSUCCESS video ([6' video](#)) was uploaded including interviews with the project partners, showing a demonstration of the industrial unit and explaining the main results and benefits of the project. The structure of this second video is as follows:

- Block I: General presentation of the project
- Block II: General presentation of the technology
- Block III: Information about methane and succinic
- Block IV: UpStream details
- Block V: DownStream details
- Block VI: Consortium and roles
- Block VII: Importance of the project

Figure 13. Both videos exceed 500 views (first video on the right, second video on the left).

KPI: 500 Video views – ACHIEVED

4.2. OFFLINE CHANNELS

CONFERENCES AND OTHER EVENTS

Apart from the dissemination carried out through digital platforms and tools, the consortium partners have attended to a series of conferences, congresses and other related events. The main goal was to spread the knowledge, disseminating the project and networking with potential interested parties (clients, experts...) in a more personal and direct way.

Due to distance reasons and pandemic restrictions, some of the events were held or attended digitally. However, in many occasions the Consortium Members assisted and presented the Project personally and live. NEOSUCCESS Consortium has attended the following events:

Table 3. List of events.

PARTNER	EVENT	DATE	PLACE	OFFLINE/ OUTLINE
AINIA	Food4Life	September 2020	Spain	ONLINE
IVEM	Bioeconomía Circular (BIOVAL)	October 2020	Spain	ONLINE
AINIA	Bioeconomy Commission (BIOVAL)	March 2021	Spain	ONLINE
DTU	Workshop on Enhanced Biogas Production & Recent Innovations (Ege University)	March 2021	Turkey	ONLINE
AINIA	EuroMembrane	November 2021	Denmark	OFFLINE
DTU	XVII World Water Congress (hybrid)	December 2021	Korea	ONLINE
AINIA	SUSCHEM	March 2022	Spain	ONLINE
AINIA	Food4Life	March 2022	Spain	ONLINE
DTU	BioRefine Cluster	May 2022	Belgium	OFFLINE
NORVENTO	Congreso Internacional de Bioenergía	October 2022	Spain	OFFLINE
IVEM	III Jornadas de Biorrefinerías	November 2022	Spain	OFFLINE
AUTH	10 th International Conference on Solid Waste Management	June 2023	Greece	OFFLINE
AUTH	HEPTA Summer School	September 2023	Greece	OFFLINE
AUTH	13 ^ο Πανελλήνιο Συνέδριο ΕΓΜΕ 2023	October 2023	Greece	OFFLINE

Figure 14. NORVENTO presenting a NEOSUCCESS poster at Congreso Internacional de Bioenergía.

Figure 15. IVEM attending the III Jornadas de Biorrefinerías.

Figure 16. Our main subcontractor AINIA presenting the project at EuroMembrane event.

Figure 17. DTU attending the BioRefine Cluster.

Figure 18. DTU online attendance to the XVII World Water Congress (hybrid).

Figure 19. AUTH at the 10th International Conference on Solid Waste Management.

KPI: Attendance to 4 events – ACHIEVED

DEMONSTRATION AND TRAINING ACTIVITIES

Demonstration and training activities were carried out in September 2023. Results of both activities are collected in D6.5 and D6.6 respectively.

- **First session – Target audience: Biogas industries**

On September 20th, IVEM and AUTH organized the [1st Seminar](#). The webinar was oriented to the biogas industries and was attended by 15 participants.

Figure 20. Screenshot of the first seminar.

KPI: 15 Attendants – ACHIEVED

- **Second session – Target audience: BioSuccinic Acid market**

Just the day after the first webinar, the [2nd webinar](#) was held (September 21st). This webinar was performed by NORVENTO and DTU and was oriented to the chemical industry and the BioSuccinic Acid market. A total of 26 participants attended the seminar.

Figure 21. Screenshot of the second seminar.

KPI: 12 Attendants – ACHIEVED

▪ **Third session – Open demonstration event**

Following both online seminars, a visit to the facilities together with a live demonstration was held on Friday, 22nd of September. The activity consisted of a short introduction, a visit to the facilities and unit, a quick live demonstration of its operation, as well as a final space for Q&A, networking and further discussions.

Figure 22. NEOSUCCESS facilities with a poster for the introduction and water for the attendants.

KPI: 20 Attendants – NOT ACHIEVED

Despite of the promotional efforts (+30 contacts with interest in the project), only 8 participants attended to the live session at IVEM's facilities. For further information, D6.5 is available.

TRAINING ACTIVITIES

AUTH and DTU prepared and delivered a comprehensive series of 3 training activities focused on the broader operational and socio-economic benefits of the developed technology. These activities were aimed at technical and managerial personnel from industry and its members, end users and stakeholders outside the consortium.

The objective of these training sessions was to educate participants on the technical and operational aspects of NEOSUCCESS, as well as the competitive and socio-economic benefits. These training sessions facilitated the understanding, acceptance and future assimilation and exploitation of the results of this project by the participating industry members and stakeholders.

The training sessions were held in parallel to the demonstration sessions (Task 6.3). To further extend the impact of the training effort beyond the consortium, an online training tool was developed and integrated into the project website.

For further information, D6.6 is also available.

KPI: 3 Activities – ACHIEVED

PRESS RELEASES

Regular press releases have been published and shared in the three Project's languages (Spanish, Greek, Danish) and English as well.

¡NEOSUCCESS CONTINÚA, LLEGANDO AL FINAL!

VALENCIA, Mayo 2023

El Proyecto NEOSUCCESS ha pasado 12 meses operando y optimizando su unidad con intención de probar la viabilidad de la tecnología en una escala industrial. Más aún, el consorcio ha trabajado en otras tareas, tales como experimentos con cepas alternativas, desarrollo de plan de negocios o actividades de diseminación.

El proyecto empezó su tercer año con una unidad recién terminada y lista para arranque (tanto el proceso de UpStream como de DownStream), así como múltiples pruebas a escala laboratorio y piloto, en las que las condiciones óptimas, los rendimientos y los resultados fueron estudiados.

Desde el último año, IVEM ha operado la unidad llevando a cabo el proceso y la tecnología NEOSUCCESS por primera vez a escala industrial. También se ha reunido, en línea y en persona, con el resto del consorcio para comentar algunas cuestiones que surgían, como la esterilización del caldo. En varias ocasiones, el resto de compañeros han visitado las instalaciones para mantenimiento, revisión de la unidad, análisis de las dificultades y optimización del proceso.

IVEM en el Fermentador Pre-Inóculo

Figure 23. Example of Press Release (in Spanish)

Table 4. Press releases publication dates

1	09/06/2021
2	27/05/2022
3	26/05/2023
4	21/11/2023

Press releases are available in the NEOSUCCESS website in its Documents section (neosuccess-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/press-release-1.zip).

KPI: 1 Press release/year – ACHIEVED

PUBLICATIONS AND ARTICLES

One of the NEOSUCCESS Project's commitments was to publish at least one scientific paper along the duration of the Project. Finalizing the Project, a total of 4 scientific papers have been published in recognized journals. In the next table, one can find information and links regarding the articles:

Table 5. NEOSUCCESS project articles.

DTU	27.08.2022	Vigato, F.; Angelidaki, I.; Woodley, J. M.; Alvarado-Morales, M.	Dissolved CO ₂ profile in bio-succinic acid production from sugars- rich industrial waste.	Biochemical Engineering Journal, 187, 108602	Link
DTU	03.04.2023	Kim, H.; Sang, B.- I.; Tsapekos, P.; Angelidaki, I.; Alvarado-Morales, M.	Techno-Economic Analysis of Succinic Acid Production from Sugar- Rich Wastewater	Energies 2023, 16, 3227	Link
IVEM	17.06.2023	López, J.C.; Monsonís, R.; López de los Mozos, E.; Heredia, F.; Gómez-Pérez, P.	Simultaneous biosuccinic production and biogas upgrading: Exploring the potential of sugar-based confectionery waste within a biorefinery concept	Bioresource Technology, Volume 384, 2023, 129362,	Link
AUTH	12.09.2023	Lithourgidis, A.; Kotsopoulos, T.; Kalamaras, S.; Skiadas, I.; Kuglarz, M.; Vigato, F.; Alvarado-Morales, M.; Angelidaki, I.	Bio-succinic acid production, up to pilot scale, by fermentation of industrial candy waste with <i>Actinobacillus</i> <i>succinogenes</i> 130Z and its downstream purification process	Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering, Volume 11, 2023, 110920	Link

KPI: At least one scientific publication – ACHIEVED

ONLINE MAGAZINES

Apart from the previously mentioned systems of dissemination, we have to add a series of publications in digital magazines. It consists of news included in the daily number of the magazine and they are:

- [Energías Renovables](#): Módulos para plantas de biogás que producen biometano y compuestos para pinturas y adhesivos (2020).
- Revista Técnica de Medio Ambiente ([RETEMA](#)): Tecnología de purificación de biogás y producción de (bio)succínico simultánea (2020).
- [ProSostenible](#): NEOSUCCESS, los ODS como motor de la innovación (2022).

Figure 24. Screenshot of an opinion piece from one of the digital magazines.

5. SUMMARY

The following tables summarize all the dissemination and communication activities that have been carried out during the project. All the targets of this activity are also collected.

Table 6. Main Dissemination Activities carried out by Project Partners (M1-M12)

ACTIVITIES M1-M12					
DATE	ACTIVITY	CHANNEL/TOOL	DESCRIPTION	PARTNER	LINK
09/07/2020	Webinar	Online Zoom	Keynote presentation – in Danish. Seminar organised by Dakofa Denmark: Title: What can we produce from biogas and other molecules from waste. Also a part of Dakofa newsletter. Denmark	DTU	Link
02/09/2020	Article	Website	PUBLICATION OF NEOSUCCESS PROJECT HIGHLIGHTS DURING AN INTERVIEW WITH JUAN CARLOS LOPEZ (AINIA) IN ENERGIAS RENOVABLES MAGAZINE	AINIA	Link
22/09/2020	Webinar	Online	PROJECT PRESENTATION at “Bioeconomía Circular: Agroalimentación” WEBINAR, organized by Bioval (Bio Cluster of the Valencian Region)	IVEM	Link
28/10/2020	Internal Meeting	Online	PROJECT PRESENTATION at Quality, Production and Sustainability working group from the Spanish Technological Platform Food for Life	AINIA	
10/2020	Magazine Article	Printed + Online	Ainia published an article in the Bioenergy Issue of RETEMA technical journal regarding NEOSUCCESS	AINIA	Link

11/2020	Newsletter	Online	1ST NEOSUCCESS NEWSLETTER: HIGHLIGHTS OF THE PROJECT	NORVENTO	Link
14/12/2020	Webinar	Online	Production of Volatile Fatty Acids from by-products	AINIA	Link
15/01/2021	Webinar	Online Zoom	Keynote presentation. Seminar organised by E2-Energy Lab of China Agricultural University and University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign. Presentation Recent advances in biomass research – China	DTU	
17/03/2021	Webinar	Online Zoom	Keynote presentation. Irimi Angelidaki Title: Biogas and future trends. Biosuccinic acid and biogas upgrading. - Turkey	DTU	Link
30/03/2021	Webinar	Online Zoom	Keynote presentation. Future technologies for production of chemicals from biogas (Greece)	DTU	
07/04/2021	Conference	Online	PROJECT PRESENTATION at Comisión de Bioeconomía de BIOVAL	AINIA	Link
06/05/2021	International Conference	Online	PROBIOREFINE 2021 Prof. Irimi Angelidaki - Technical University of Denmark, Denmark "Biotechnology as a Tool for Capturing and Recycling CO2"	DTU	Link

Table 7. Main Dissemination Activities carried out by Project Partners (M13-M42).

ACTIVITIES M13-M42					
DATE	ACTIVITY	CHANNEL/TOOL	DESCRIPTION	PARTNER	LINK
27/08/2022	Article	Biochemical Engineering Journal, 187, 108602	Dissolved CO ₂ profile in bio-succinic acid production from sugars-rich industrial waste	DTU	Link
09/2022	Video	YouTube	NEOSUCCESS Project (EU H2020): Short video (2-3') to raise awareness about the sustainable production of BioSuccinic Acid and BioMethane	CONSORTIUM	Link
06/10/2022	Congress	Offline	NORVENTO presenting a Neosuccess poster at Congreso Internacional de Bioenergía (Spain)	NORVENTO	Link
17/10/2022	Article	Website	Ainia published the article at PROSOSTENIBLE: NEOSUCCESS, los ODS como motor de la innovación	AINIA	Link
11/2022	Conference	Offline	IVEM presenting Neosuccess at III Jornadas de Biorrefinerías (Spain)	IVEM	Link
11/2022	Congress	Offline	AINIA presenting the project at EuroMembrane event	AINIA	
03/04/2023	Article	Energies Journal 2023, 16, 3227	Techno-Economic Analysis of Succinic Acid Production from Sugar-Rich Wastewater	DTU	Link

05/2023	Video	YouTube	NEOSUCCESS: Simultaneous Biogas Purification and Succinic Production: Long video (6') interviewing the project partners, showing the demonstration unit and explaining the main results and benefits of the project	CONSORTIUM	Link
17/06/2023	Article	Bioresource Technology, Volume 384, 2023, 129362	Simultaneous biosuccinic production and biogas upgrading: Exploring the potential of sugar-based confectionery waste within a biorefinery concept	IVEM	Link
12/09/2023	Article	Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering, Volume 11, 2023, 110920	Bio-succinic acid production, up to pilot scale, by fermentation of industrial candy waste with <i>Actinobacillus succinogenes</i> 130Z and its downstream purification process	AUTH	Link
20/09/2023	Webinar	Online Teams	1 st Session of the promotional activities. Webinar oriented to the biogas industries (15 attendants)	IVEM & AUTH	Link
21/09/2023	Webinar	Online Teams	2 nd Session of the promotional activities. Webinar oriented to the chemical industry and the BioSuccinic Acid market (26 attendants)	NORVENTO & DTU	Link
22/09/2023	Visit	Offline	3 rd session of the promotional activities. Presential activity at the NEOSUCCESS pilot plant located at the WWTP in Paterna, Valencia. This demonstration shows in more detail the production process.	IVEM	Link
17/10/2023 26/10/2023	Videos	YouTube	1 st and 2 nd Training Videos uploaded on YouTube (open access) as the 3 rd training activity, explaining the details of the USP and DSP process and units.	AUTH & DTU	Link 1 Link 2

Table 8. Summary of the targets for the D&C actions.

Online channels	Target audience	Target description	Target number	Result
Webpage	All audiences	Web active since M3 of the NEOSUCCESS. Content updated	1,000 visits/year	ACHIEVED
Audio visual materials	All audiences	Production of 2 informative videos	500 views	ACHIEVED
Newsletters	Industry, academia, policy makers	Periodic newsletters with relevant news and updates of the NEOSUCCESS	Twice a year	ACHIEVED
Social media Twitter	All audiences	Engagement with the general audiences and its concerns. Production of visual attractive content tailored to the platform	200 followers	ACHIEVED
Social media LinkedIn	Industry, academia, policy makers	Engagement with the Industry, academia, policy makers and its concerns. Production of visual attractive content tailored to the platform	200 followers	ACHIEVED
Social media YouTube	All audiences	Dissemination of NEOSUCCESS' audio-visual materials	500 views per video	ACHIEVED
Offline channels	Target audience	Target description	Target number	Result
Trade shows & Fairs, Congresses, Summits	Industry (BioMethane and BioSA)	Participation in relevant trade shows. For example: The World Biogas Summit; Bio 360 Expo; CO2 Reuse Summit; World Biomaterials Congress; The World Biogas EXPO 2020	4	ACHIEVED
Demonstrations sessions	Industry, academia, policy makers	Demonstration Sessions organised by NEOSUCCESS. These events will help disseminate	3 (*)	ACHIEVED
Training sessions	Industry, academia, policy makers	Training Sessions organised by NEOSUCCESS. These events will help disseminate NEOSUCCESS and its results (Organised in parallel with Demonstration sessions)	3	ACHIEVED
Mixed channels	Target audience	Target description	Target number	Result
Press Releases	All audiences	NEOSUCCESS will publish press releases to inform of the progress and milestones of NEOSUCCESS	1 per year	ACHIEVED
D&C Materials	All audiences	D&C materials included tailored designs for: Leaflets, Posters, Roll ups, the NEOSUCCESS summary document and the Promotional Stand	5 different materials designed	ACHIEVED
Scientific publications	Industry, academia, policy makers	Scientific journals	1 publication	ACHIEVED

* The targets for the demonstration session was achieved since 3 demonstration activities were carried out, however the KPI related to the n^o of attendants was not reached in the 3rd session.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The Dissemination & Communication activities have been a success, far exceeding the targets set at the beginning. All the members of the consortium have been involved so that the project could reach as many people as possible, from all sectors and types of audiences.

Up to the date, 4 scientific papers have been published; the prepared videos overpassed 1.600 views (both together); several promotion and training activities were carried out reaching a considerable amount of people online and offline; website has received around 5.000 visits; and the Consortium has participated in almost a dozen events.

All of this in the intra-european and extra-european contexts, in the research and academic niches as well as in the industry and professional fields, reaching a wide range of audiences along the whole Project's time. Furthermore, the website will still be available, as well as the YouTube videos and other contents, hence disseminating even after the Project's end.

Figure 25. 1st seminar YouTube video, accumulating views after its closure.

INDEX OF FIGURES AND TABLES

FIGURES

Figure 1. NEOSUCCESS Partners & WP6 (D&C) effort.	6
Figure 2. NORVENTO's visit to operate the DSP together with IVEM at the Paterna WWTP.	8
Figure 3. Both Universities visit the WWTP to record the second NEOSUCCESS video and run the USP.	9
Figure 4. Consortium meeting at NEOSUCCESS pilot, Paterna's WWTP.	9
Figure 5. Online consortium meeting.	10
Figure 6. <i>Headline of the website</i>	11
Figure 7. Country distribution.	11
Figure 8. Screenshot of the website section where new posts are uploaded.	12
Figure 9. <i>Example of cover of the NEOSUCCESS newsletter</i>	12
Figure 10. <i>Screenshot of the Twitter's profile</i>	13
Figure 11. Screenshots of the Project's LinkedIn.	14
Figure 12. Screenshot of the YouTube account.	15
Figure 13. Both videos exceed 500 views (first video on the right, second video on the left). ..	15
Figure 14. NORVENTO presenting a NEOSUCCESS poster at Congreso Internacional de Bioenergía.	17
Figure 15. IVEM attending the III Jornadas de Biorrefinerías.	17
Figure 16. Our main subcontractor AINIA presenting the project at EuroMembrane event.	17
Figure 17. DTU attending the BioRefine Cluster.	18
Figure 18. DTU online attendance to the XVII World Water Congress (hybrid).	18
Figure 19. AUTH at the 10 th International Conference on Solid Waste Management.	18
Figure 20. Screenshot of the first seminar.	19
Figure 21. Screenshot of the second seminar.	19
Figure 22. NEOSUCCESS facilities with a poster for the introduction and water for the attendants.	20
Figure 23. Example of Press Release (in Spanish)	21
Figure 24. Screenshot of an opinion piece from one of the digital magazines.	23
Figure 25. 1 st seminar YouTube video, accumulating views after its closure.	29

TABLES

Table 1. List of events.	16
Table 2. NEOSUCCESS project articles.	22
Table 3. Main Dissemination Activities carried out by Project Partners (M1-M12)	24
Table 4. Main Dissemination Activities carried out by Project Partners (M13-M42).	26
Table 5. Summary of the targets for the D&C actions.	28